

Table S1. Outcome measures at each time point in the 29 patients, classified by type of eating disorder.

Outcome Measure	Baseline Mean (SD)	Week 4 Mean (SD)	Week 8 Mean (SD)	Week 12 Mean (SD)	Week 16 Mean (SD)	<i>p</i> ^a	η_G^2 ^b
BED (n = 22)							
Bing-eating episodes/4 weeks ^c	57.7 (48.5)	38.5 (33.7)	27.7 (24.1)	17.6 (21.5)	11.2 (19.7)	< 0.001	0.223
Binge-eating days/4 weeks ^c	21.2 (6.7)	18.5 (8.7)	15.4 (9.1)	10.6 (9.8)	6.4 (9.6)	< 0.001	0.274
EDE-Q score							
Global	3.1 (1.0)	2.3 (1.1)	2.1 (1.1)	2.0 (1.0)	1.9 (1.2)	< 0.001	0.131
Restraint	0.8 (1.0)	0.8 (1.1)	0.9 (1.0)	1.1 (1.2)	0.9 (1.1)	0.631	0.009
Eating concern	3.4 (1.6)	1.8 (1.3)	1.3 (1.0)	1.1 (0.7)	1.0 (0.9)	< 0.001	0.382
Shape concern	4.2 (1.3)	3.4 (1.6)	3.1 (1.7)	3.1 (1.6)	3.0 (1.8)	< 0.001	0.070
Weight concern	4.0 (1.4)	3.0 (1.5)	2.9 (1.6)	2.8 (1.5)	2.7 (1.7)	< 0.001	0.088
QIDS-SR ₁₆ score	16.8 (5.4)	13.9 (5.2)	11.5 (4.7)	10.8 (4.6)	9.5 (6.0)	< 0.001	0.207
BMI, kg/m ²	25.9 (5.2)	25.9 (5.1)	25.8 (5.3)	25.8 (5.2)	25.6 (5.2)	0.239	0.000
Weight, kg	68.2 (19.0)	68.3 (19.0)	68.2 (19.7)	68.3 (19.7)	67.6 (19.3)	0.286	0.000
Biochemical variables							
Zinc, µg/dL	90.6 (9.5)	119.7 (38.6)	114.6 (19.4)	112.0 (30.5)	108.3 (24.3)	0.001	0.127
Copper, µg/dL	119.5 (32.8)	109.9 (22.6)	118.1 (39.9)	118.2 (40.3)	119.1 (35.5)	0.840	0.003
Copper/zinc ratio	1.3 (0.4)	1.0 (0.3)	1.1 (0.5)	1.2 (0.6)	1.2 (0.5)	0.004	0.048
Ferritin, ng/mL	81.52 (79.62)	78.64 (76.12)	75.24 (73.95)	71.23 (79.43)	79.38 (93.85)	0.671	0.002
Iron, µg/dL	74.2 (27.9)	75.3 (28.9)	83.1 (31.6)	66.8 (30.1)	91.1 (44.1)	0.016	0.066

Table S1. (conti.)**BN (n = 7)**

Binge-eating episodes/4 weeks ^c	34.9 (19.4)	29.0 (24.0)	27.6 (26.6)	18.9 (14.3)	17.6 (17.7)	0.017	0.102
Binge-eating days/4 weeks ^c	19.1 (6.6)	15.9 (9.2)	15.6 (9.4)	12.7 (9.3)	12.4 (11.0)	0.025	0.076
EDE-Q score							
Global	3.3 (0.9)	2.8 (1.1)	2.9 (1.3)	3.0 (1.2)	2.6 (1.4)	0.243	0.041
Restraint	1.6 (1.0)	2.1 (1.5)	2.5 (1.7)	2.8 (2.2)	2.0 (1.8)	0.217	0.068
Eating concern	4.2 (1.4)	3.0 (1.5)	2.9 (1.6)	2.8 (1.5)	2.5 (1.7)	0.011	0.138
Shape concern	3.8 (1.6)	3.2 (2.1)	3.3 (1.9)	3.6 (1.5)	3.1 (1.9)	0.420	0.020
Weight concern	3.5 (1.9)	2.9 (1.8)	3.0 (2.1)	2.8 (1.8)	2.5 (1.9)	0.170	0.031
QIDS-SR ₁₆ score	17.6 (4.8)	15.4 (5.9)	11.7 (5.1)	12.3 (7.0)	12.6 (7.2)	0.002	0.136
BMI, kg/m ²	21.4 (2.7)	21.3 (2.7)	21.3 (2.8)	20.9 (2.9)	20.8 (3.0)	0.102	0.008
Weight, kg	60.0 (10.2)	59.9 (10.5)	59.8 (10.3)	58.5 (9.7)	58.3 (9.5)	0.088	0.006
Biochemical variables							
Zinc, µg/dL	86.0 (10.6)	113.2 (23.8)	108.2 (47.1)	104.8 (23.9)	118.4 (42.8)	0.150	0.155
Copper, µg/dL	117.4 (40.5)	115.3 (24.0)	106.5 (33.0)	112.8 (32.9)	105.9 (23.1)	0.412	0.026
Copper/zinc ratio	1.4 (0.5)	1.0 (0.2)	1.2 (0.6)	1.2 (0.5)	1.0 (0.5)	0.116	0.092
Ferritin, ng/mL	109.16 (68.90)	95.58 (64.29)	86.25 (61.31)	89.17 (91.34)	111.60 (79.46)	0.963	0.003
Iron, µg/dL	91.7 (54.1)	98.5 (40.9)	99.8 (39.2)	83.0 (27.6)	101.7 (43.3)	0.730	0.041

^a Data on changes over the study period were statistically analyzed by repeated-measures analysis of variance (ANOVA). ^b Effective size was calculated as generalized eta squared (η_G^2). ^c Includes both objective and subjective binge eating.

BED, binge-eating disorder; BN, bulimia nervosa; EDE-Q, the Eating Disorder Examination-Questionnaire; QIDS-SR₁₆, the 16-item Quick Inventory of Depressive Symptomatology (Self-Report); BMI, body mass index.